

FORMATION AND IMPLEMENTATION OF FINANCIAL OBLIGATIONS

Shaxnoza Shukurovna Raxmatova

Termez State University

teacher of the Department of Finance, Uzbekistan

Abstract: All the activities of the state are connected with finance. Their importance has especially increased in connection with the acquisition of state sovereignty of the Republic of Uzbekistan and when the society focused on the formation of a market economy, free movement of goods, services and financial resources, support for competition and freedom of economic activity. Constitutional recognition and State protection of all forms of property have become more important than ever.

Keywords: employee, financial relations, financial reporting, organizational support, statistics, control, audit.

Introduction. In the business, everyday sphere, the concept of debt often appears. Financial obligations are understood as a legal relationship related to the transfer of finance in its pure form from one person to another or the exchange of assets on obviously unfavorable terms for the debtor. Let's consider the main types, characteristics of financial liabilities, the conditions of their occurrence and repayment.

Definition

Everyone is familiar with the concept of debt, obligations. This term does not always include an object that has an estimate, cost measurement, or quality characteristic. For example, a mother has a parental duty to her son, a citizen is obliged to protect their homeland, pay taxes, and residents pay utility companies for services.

First of all, it is important to find out what financial obligations are. This is an aspect of the civil-legal relations of individuals or legal entities, expressed in monetary terms. One subject of legal relations has the right to claim, and the second fulfills the obligation to transfer assets. In simple terms, a debt obligation is a specific amount of debt owed by one counterparty to another.

The debt can be formed by agreement and non-contractual legal relations, according to regulatory legal acts. For example, a borrower receives a loan from a bank and under the terms of the contract undertakes to return the funds within the established time frame. When a taxpayer purchases a car, he must annually transfer a certain amount of transport tax to the regional budget.

From a legal point of view, the property relations of the parties are formed on the right to claim money, certain material goods. The obligations of the enterprise and citizens according to the criteria belong to the group of requirements described in Article 307 of the Civil Code of the Russian Federation. The subject of legal relations is not only claims for the return of capital, property, and valuables, but also the refusal to perform such actions.

The objects of the relationship are:

executive authorities;

Central Bank of the Russian Federation;

international financial and credit organizations;

securities market participants;

insurance agents;

asset managers for financing;

pension non-state, state, investment funds;

professional participants in the turnover of financial instruments, excluding consultants;

users of commodity exchanges, etc.

Formation sources

Monetary obligations are formed according to legal facts or the norms of the Civil Code of the Russian Federation. Let's list the popular reasons for the formation of FIN. liabilities, borrowed assets:

Contracts-are concluded between individuals or legal entities, the subject of the agreement is services, goods, labor activities and other types of work and agreements.

Unilateral transactions – actions performed by a particular person, form obligations exclusively for him, other citizens and corporations do not participate in the calculations.

Acts of public authority – any legislative codes that have entered into force by decision of state or municipal bodies.

The fact of causing harm to another person – moral, material damage, estimated in monetary terms.

Legal facts, events – for example, an emergency is an insured event and obliges the insurer to pay compensation to the client.

Characteristic features

Monetary obligations have specific criteria and parameters:

The debt can be performed by the borrower exclusively in the form of finance, the provision of goods and services is not allowed.

The payment instrument is any official monetary unit agreed upon by the parties to the relationship (Russian, foreign currency, etc.). It is allowed to repay the debt in cash or non-cash payments.

In the contract, the normative legal act, the goal achieved in the performance of the obligation, etc. is predetermined.

Classification

The legislation of Uzbekistan does not regulate a specific approach to the specific differentiation of monetary obligations of citizens, commercial, non-commercial, state-owned institutions. Dozens of different attributes are taken as the basis for grouping in financial law. The simplest classification of debts is by the time of occurrence. Short-term debt does not exist for more than twelve months, and long-term debt can last for years.

Upon the exchange of funds

There are two types of relationships: those related to the actual transfer of values and the objects of the transaction, valued in monetary terms. The first type includes a loan agreement, and the second type includes payment for mobile communication and Internet services from Rostelecom.

Financial legal relations that are implemented by transferring money from one person to another as a fulfillment of the main condition of the agreement are divided into separate groups. For example, in the legal sphere, the most common obligations are formed upon the conclusion of purchase and sale transactions, payment for services, and works.

Deposit when making a deposit, certain financial obligations also arise

Let's list several groups of legal relations, when the subject of the transaction is money:

Making a contribution to the authorized capital of a legal entity.

Regular income received from the turnover of capital, valuables (rent).

Mutual funds, investment contributions for a specific project.

Factoring operations.

Trading in bank products (loans, deposits, deposits, loans) , etc.

According to the legal relationship, there are simple, complex, and interdependent obligations. An example of a simple debt is the transfer of money from one citizen to another on a promissory note. Most relationships in the financial market are closely intertwined, and counterparties have mutual requirements. Settlements are intended for mutually beneficial exchange of assets, services, and goods.

Connection to the personality

Among the classification features, belonging to a person is also distinguished. For example, in the event of the death of an individual, the debt will cease to exist or will be inherited by his close relatives. Although in the inheritance case, there are also exceptions based on personal affiliation. For example, intellectual or creative abilities cannot be inherited. Individual skills belong exclusively to the individual. The heir will not be able to write music, a picture, or make a film for a deceased relative.

Rights and obligations that are not directly linked to the individual may be assigned to other counterparties. For example, as a result of the reorganization of the enterprise, the succession of accounts payable is carried out. With the simultaneous participation of several creditors and debtors, a multiple active or passive obligation is formed, respectively. At the same time, each of the members of the agreement bears shared responsibility.

Other criteria

According to the degree of dependence, the main and additional obligations are distinguished. For example, if a citizen buys a house under a mortgage, he will be the main defendant under the contract. Since the amount of debt is substantial, the bank will require a guarantee. The guarantor will act as an auxiliary payer.

References:

1. Raxmatova, S. S. (2020). Features of accounting in the service sector. ISJ Theoretical & Applied Science, 11 (91), 332-336.
2. Rakhimov, G. M., & Safarov, J. (2021). AUDIT OF SETTLEMENTS WITH SUPPLIERS AND CONTRACTORS: THE MAIN STAGES OF ITS IMPLEMENTATION AND THE SPECIFICS OF PERFORMING AUDIT PROCEDURES. Theoretical & Applied Science, (4), 443-445.
3. Гўзалбегим Рахимова (2021). Учет результатов последующей переоценки имущества, завода, машин и оборудования в соответствие международных стандартов. Общество и инновации, 2 (3/S), 111-121. doi: 10.47689/2181-1415-vol2-iss3/S-pp111-121
4. Murodovna, R. G. (2021). Analytical procedure in an audit of fixed assets. International Journal of Financial Management and Economics International Journal of Financial Management and Economics, 4(1), 41-45P.
5. Rakhimova, G. M. (2021) Analytical procedure in an audit of fixed assets.//International Journal of Financial Management and Economics. Volume 4, Issue1, Page Number 41-45.
6. Rakhimova, G. Accounting of the results of continuous revaluation of property, plant and equipment in accordance with international standards// Society and innovations Special Issue – 3 (2021) / ISSN 2181-1415
7. Raximova, G. M., Abdulxayeva, S., & Pirimkulov, O. M. (2020). Features of audit of small and medium-sized enterprises. Theoretical & Applied Science, №. 6, pp.101-105.
8. Raximova, G. M. (2020). Problems of accounting and audit of fixed assets. International Scientific Journal ISJ Theoretical& Applied Science, Philadelphia, USA, №. 05.
9. Rahimova, G. M. (2020). Praktika ucheta i audita osnovnyh sredstv. Problemy sovremennoj nauki i obrazovanija, №. 7 (152).
10. Abdullayev, A., Yusupova, M. Raximova, G. (2020) Buxgalteriya hisobi. Darslik. 494.p